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**Interrogating Indigenous Knowledge and Ecology: A
Colonial and Postcolonial Ecocritical Study of Janice
Pariat's *Everything the Light Touches***

By

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Abstract

India has a very traditional wisdom of living harmoniously with the world. The vision of geopiety, of envisaging a cosmos governed by 'Rita', Sanskrit for rhythm, the impersonal underlying order, and regulator of all life on Earth. In this worldview human or nonhuman does not stand apart but is yoked by 'Rita' in a relationship of interdependence and interrelationship with nature. Folktales, oral traditions, and mythologies corroborate this integral bond between humans and nature embedded in agricultural cycles, the flex of seasons the alternating wet and dry spells, and the regularity of the cosmic order celebrated and emphasized through sacred ritual, art, and architecture. Janice Pariat in her latest novel *Everything the Light Touches* takes us away from Linnaeus's nomenclature of fixing and categorizing science to Goethean science of freeing and unifying thereby employing an alternate view of understanding the environment by forcing us to look beyond one race - the human race because the world is weighing under the penury of it. This tussle is evident in our notion of the indigenous where their knowledge systems give us a different scope of viewing nature which is in stark contrast to the Anthropocene. This research aims at understanding these centuries-old traditions of generosity and gratitude towards nature that are proclaimed in the tribal culture of the northeast which was vastly exploited during the colonial rule and the legacy of slow violence continues in the postcolonial period by exploiting the land and its resources.

Keywords: colonial, postcolonial ecocriticism, Anthropocene, biophilia, indigenous knowledge systems.

Introduction

“Jungles and grasslands are the logical destinations, and towns and farmlands are the labyrinths that people have imposed between them sometime in the past. I cherish the green enclaves accidentally left behind” (Wilson 1984, 6)

The introduction and popularization of the biophilia hypothesis by Edward O. Wilson in his book *Biophilia* (1984) have pointed toward human being's “innate tendency to focus on life and lifelike processes.” (1) The inclination toward ‘biophilia’ becomes apparent in the anticipated dreams and reactions of people from a young age onwards. This inclination perpetuates recurrent cultural patterns across all societies. The human brain is characterized by how swiftly and resolutely it can acquire specific knowledge about particular types of flora and fauna. (85) “Our intrinsic emotions drive us to search for fresh habitats, to cross unexplored terrain, but we still crave the sense of a mysterious world stretching infinitely beyond.” (76) Biophilia is not just a scientific concept, but also has important implications for ethics and spirituality, and can help us form a more holistic understanding of our place in the world because “the natural world is the refuge of the spirit, remote, static, richer even than human

imagination.” (11) It is a meeting ground for humanists and scientists, where the “humanists are the shamans of the intellectual tribe, wise men who interpret knowledge and transmit the folklore, rituals, and sacred texts. Scientists are the scouts and hunters.” (58) Together they offer several ways to lessen the modern alienation from nature which not only degrades the beauty and joy of human life but also triggers environmental irresponsibility and apathy. Yet in this Anthropocene epoch, we are hardly able to “exist in this paradise without the machine that tears it apart. We are killing the thing we love, our Eden, progenitrix and sibyl.” (12) The word ‘Anthropocene’ popularized by Dutch chemist Paul Crutzen to describe this destruction of the planet due to human interference. “Considering these and many other major and still growing impacts of human activities on earth and atmosphere, and at all, including global, scales, it thus is more than appropriate to emphasize the central role of mankind in geology and ecology by using the term ‘Anthropocene’ for the current geological epoch.” (Crutzen 2006, 15) Such examples of human interference can be found everywhere, but the fight against this interference exists in the life narratives of eco-warriors like Mayilamma, the Late Mrs. Spelity Lyngdoh Langrin, etc. Mayilamma’s life story maps the rise of environmental activism in Kerala; and Kong Spelity’s in Meghalaya. The narratives of these eco-warriors “weave(s) into its rhetoric the realities of consumption, globalization, widening socio-economic inequalities and rising ecological burdens borne by the marginalized poor.” The stories of these two earth carers resonate with the “oiko-autobiographies emerging from the fissured earthscapes of the Global South and the environmentally traumatized pockets of the North.” A frail, fifty-year-old adivasi widow, Mayilamma, “fought for the cause of the small village of Plachimada on the Kerala-Tamilnadu border, became a symbol of global resistance against Coca-Cola.” (Rangarajan 2018, xxiii-xxv) In the 2020 issue of *Down to Earth*, an environmental magazine, Tarun Bharatiya familiarized us about Kong Spelity, 95 years old matriarch of Domiasiat, a small village in Meghalaya who refused to surrender her land to the Uranium Corporation of India Ltd (UCIL) even though she was offered 1.5 crores annually for 30 years. For her “selling the land would be selling her freedom and could the money buy this river, this land, this waterfall.” (Bharatiya, *Remembering Kong Spelity Lyngdoh Langrin*, 2020) Such is the power of “the environmentalism of the poor” writes Rob Nixon in *Slow Violence and the Environmentalism of the Poor* (2011) which remains unaltered by “resource imperialism inflicted on the global south to maintain the unsustainable consumer appetites of rich-country citizens and, increasingly, of the urban middle classes in the global South itself.” The shifting of environmental problems, whether happening quickly or gradually, has a significant effect on people who rely on small resource areas for their livelihoods. These areas are far from the

wealthy regions that exploit the world's resources on a large scale, and this has a strong impact on both ecosystems and the people who depend on them. (22)

Gordon L Miller's introduction to Goethe's *The Metamorphosis of Plants* (2009) advocates for such understanding of the essence of natural things through not only our usage of physical senses but also our intuition and imagination. This requires a balance between our sensory perception and our inner perception. Goethe's scientific approach aims to attain a profound understanding that originates from within. This method of acquiring knowledge is based on a synchronization or agreement between the human spirit and the enlightening spirit of nature, where a single spirit communicates with the other. (xviii) Goethe acknowledged the importance of Linnaeus's Binomial Nomenclature, in the process of "systemic classification in bringing a sense of order to the teeming multitudes of flora and fauna" yet this mechanical multifarious terminology could not quite apprehend the "enduring essence of plant life" and the recognition of which propelled Goethe "beyond the Linnaean world of fixed forms and species and into a new world of transformation and evolution." (xxii-xxiii)

"The United Nations estimates that there are over 370 million indigenous people living in 72 countries worldwide. This would equate to over 6% of the total world population that includes at least 5000 distinct communities." Substantial among these are the indigenous people in India comprising an estimated population of 10.43 crore or 8.60% constitutionally recognized as "Scheduled Tribes." They occupy over 18.70% of India's total geographical area. (Kattimati, 34) These indigenous people have a deep-rooted belief in the interdependent relationship between nature, spirits, and humans. They possess the ability to connect the visible with the invisible, the animate with the inanimate, enabling them to perceive the unseen and unheard, thus embracing the mystical world as a reality. Their lives are intimately intertwined with the external environment, which is highly valued as a communal treasure. Nature is regarded as a precious gift from the spirits and is, therefore, revered and worshipped. Mountains, forests, earth, water, and trees are among the entities they venerate. There resides a Goethean scientist in every indigenous person who lives in close affinity with nature taking from nature and giving in return nurture and care. Mahia Maurial in her essay *Indigenous Knowledge and Schooling* (1999) renders three points to explain indigenous knowledge, that it is local, holistic, and agrapha (oral). It is local because of "the result of the quotidian interaction in indigenous people's territories" which is "recreated through generations" in the form of oral stories, agrarian work on the land, tending plants, during special events, etc. It is a lived culture, practiced every day through generations. It acquired the term holistic because their knowledge

is “produced and reproduced within human relationships as well as in their relationship with nature.” According to Hispanic anthropology, *Agrafa* “refers to societies that did not invent or incorporate originally written expression in their culture.” They maintain a sophisticated oral tradition recreated daily from parents to children and elders to youngsters. (63) One such example is the oral culture practiced in many indigenous communities in North East India that is “founded on narratives of creation, myth of origin, tales of different types and in almost all communities, migration stories.” (Syiem 2016, 81) A sense of organic rootedness in the processes of nature is exhibited in every social aspect of tribal life. Due to their “long and continued interaction with their immediate environment” writes Kattimani, the tribal people have “acquired a broad knowledge base of the behaviour of complex ecological systems of their localities.” Their knowledge consists of a “cumulative body of rituals, beliefs, practices, and adaptive strategies, handed down through generations by vertical oral transmission determines their cultural ethos, value system, and world-view.” (51) This knowledge rendered a severe blow during the colonial period. Colonialism was an instrument for extracting either resources or people uprooting them from one place and into another. This restitution itself is a very difficult thing because not only are their culture and tradition being uprooted but also their bodies and resources. Postcolonial studies regarded indigenous populations as a mere part of nature and consequently treated them as tools or animals, these populations were gradually assimilated into Western perspectives on the environment. This process makes it challenging, if not impossible, to achieve restoration in both cultural and environmental aspects.

The forest cover of Meghalaya is 80% green surpassing the average in India by more than threefold, and a total of 79 sacred groves are virgin forest patches pointed out by Rekha M. Shangpliang in her book *Forests in the Life of Khasis*. (2010) She states that “the supernatural connotations of forest have occupied an important place in Khasi literature, Khasi legends and folktales and the life and culture of the people as a whole”. One walk in the evergreen woods “reveals a grand epic that unfolds the region’s oral history that is attuned to forest”. (29-30) The forest myths of the Khasi community in Meghalaya exemplify a remarkable connection between humans, mythology, and the environment, highlighting the diverse purposes that myths serve in societies worldwide. Through the transmission of myths, and folklore to younger generations, the Khasi community has fostered a lasting relationship between humanity and the natural world. “It is a Khasi custom to believe that the Earth with all its bounty is referred to as ‘Meiramew’ which means ‘Mother Earth’, ‘Meiramew’ being a combination of land, forests, rivers, and streams, the Khasis do not separate these elements of

the mother and the Earth as separate entities.” (xiii) This idea reverberates in the book *Braiding Sweetgrass* (2013) by Robin Wall Kimmerer where she points to the fact that the trees in the forest are an interconnected “subterranean networks of mycorrhizae, fungal strands that inhabit tree roots.” The interdependence of the fungus and the trees is astonishing because “the mycorrhizal symbiosis enables the fungi to forage for mineral nutrients in the soil and deliver them to the tree in exchange for carbohydrates.” The mycorrhizae undergo a bridge making process using the fungi between individual trees to connect all the trees there. Kimmerer calls the fungi “Robin Hood” as “they take from the rich and give to the poor so that all the trees arrive at the same carbon surplus at the same time.” This symbiosis points to the fact that all that is thriving with life in this world is yoked together into interdependence. “All flourishing is mutual. Soil, fungus, tree, squirrel, boy-all are the beneficiaries of reciprocity.” (20)

At the sacred sites of Nongkrem and Mawphlang in Meghalaya are the sacred groves, believed to be the house of indigenous deities of Lyngdoh and the Syiem clans. These sites not only represent the profound faith of the people but also serve as a plea for social and ecological responsibility in the face of human demands. Myths hold the wisdom and values of the indigenous community. Although these myths were passed orally and influenced by social perspectives, they still illuminate the lives and wisdom of past generations. At this vital point when the world is trying to strive for a balance foregrounding the interdependent relationship between humans and the environment, the Khasi community stands as an example of achieving this harmony at the same time preserving this knowledge for future generations who will inherit this remarkable land. This paper is an attempt to understand the indigenous knowledge systems of the Khasis from the point of view of the colonial and postcolonial ecocritical perspectives by learning the histories of the land and also the present scenarios.

Pariat’s *Everything the Light Touches*: An Artefact of Indigenous Knowledge System studied Ecocritically

Ecocriticism, as Cheryll Glotfelty in her book *The Ecocriticism Reader* (1996) states “is the study of the relationship between literature and the physical environment.” Every human culture is unique and, in some way, or another is affected by the over-exploitation of nature. “Ecocriticism takes as its subject the interconnections between nature and culture, specifically the cultural artifacts of language and literature. As a critical stance, it has one foot in literature and the other on land; as a theoretical discourse, it negotiates between the human and the nonhuman.” Glotfelty provides Barry Commoner’s statement of species interconnectedness

thereby pointing toward the fact that literature cannot be studied in a vacuum “but, rather, plays a part in an immensely complex global system, in which energy, matter, and ideas interact.” (xviii-xix) Postcolonial ecocriticism endeavours to comprehensively grasp the mechanisms through which nature was manipulated, structured, planned, displaced, and exploited. It aims to foster an awareness that prevents the automatic labelling of individuals closely connected to nature as inherently lesser. “One of the central tasks of postcolonial ecocriticism as an emergent field has been to contest - also to provide viable alternatives to - western ideologies of development.” (Huggan et al 2006, 29) Janice Pariat’s novel *Everything the Light Touches* resonates with these notions of ecocritical and postcolonial ecocritical study where the indigenous knowledge systems that are found in Khasi culture has one foot in myth and folklore and the other on nature. Ecocriticism as a theoretical discourse, negotiates in Pariat’s novel, between the human and the nonhuman, both are enmeshed in an everlasting relationship in which the tribals in the remote villages of Meghalaya refuse to instrumentalize nature of their own accord. The postcolonial ecocritical study provides us with this framework to understand how certain values have shaped our lives, that extracting trees, uprooting them for timber, for modernity, is not the appropriate way of life. Pariat provides these viable alternatives to Western attitudes towards materialistic development thereby proving that the indigenous knowledge system is not primitive. It is environmentally positive in every sense. In the novel Evelyn and Shai make a journey to the heart of Meghalaya, one in the colonial and another in the postcolonial period respectively. In this journey, they deliberately free themselves from the constraints of rigidity to openminded discourses with the tribals. Through their adventures, they undergo a process of defamiliarizing nature wherein that, which was once mundane for them transforms and thrives with fecundity and purpose. Pariat rightly says:

That everything you see for the first time you see for the last time, because either the view changes, or you do. (36)

There are four specific journeys mentioned in the novel in varied time frames and no particular order. The first is the present-day journey of Shai narrated in first person, wary of her stay in Delhi where it is “four seventy-seven AQI and counting” (5) she goes to Shillong her hometown thereafter venturing to Mawmalang, and Domiasiat, two remote villages in Meghalaya where no proper roads exist to connect it with Shillong. The next section gives us a peep into the life of Evelyn, a botanist academic, inspired by the life of Goethe and the travelogues of Joseph Dalton Hooker (a 19th-century explorer), who makes a journey to colonial India and thereafter to Cherrapunjee. Interspersing these two fictional narratives are

two historically factual narratives adapted by Pariat for a kaleidoscopic story-telling method braiding together narrative and historical fiction. While one tells the tale of Goethe's 1787 tour of Italy, which prompted him to write his first scientific work, *The Metamorphosis of Plants*, the other is of Swedish botanist Carl Linnaeus's famous expedition to Lapland in 1732 resulting in his book *Flora Lapponica*. Evelyn and Goethe's stories are told in the third person by an omniscient narrator who is not only aware of the geographical routes they travel but also the routes of their thoughts. Pariat presents a highly imaginative segment in the text where Linnaeus's journey to Lapland is recounted through a blend of verse, poetry, and prose. This section acts as an interlude, bridging the desires of the characters and their search for solace in their heritage, exploration of new territories for scientific enlightenment, and the quest for a harmonious blend of philosophy and modern science to gain a deeper understanding of our existence. Starting from Carl Linnaeus, where the idea of segregation of different parts of plants and systemic nomenclature is metamorphosed by Goethe into "all is leaf." (270) In the section 'Carl', Pariat writes the poem describing the ideas of Linnaeus about the qualities of a true botanist, she states:

This much is clear-
have a real understanding of botany,
and know how to name all plants with intelligible names.
Then, be either of two things:
collectors or methodizers. The first,
concerned primarily with the number
of species of plants.
The second with the arrangement
of plants and nomenclature. (215)

This in turn is modified by Goethe in the section 'Johann' of the novel. Pariat writes:

Where classification separates and fixes and deadens, metamorphosis allows for life.

The natural world is no machine, Moritz, he adds smilingly. It is alive. (271)

This idea of Goethe is further modified into an "archetypal plant" because he, in his wanderings through Sicily gardens found out that even though there is a distinct difference in the shapes of the leaves, flowers yet they somehow morph into one another and form one single archetypal plant. "The archetypal plant that carries within it all plants of the past, present, and future." (304)

Evelyn's botanical research at Cambridge and her in-depth inquiries about the natural world made her join the Goethean Science Society there, which propagated his ideas of metamorphosis and the archetypal plant. Her browsing through Joseph Dalton Hooker's *Himalayan Journals* piqued her curiosity. Hooker's Journal stated of a "Diengiei" found in the Khasi mountains that the locals called the first tree, "The tree that held all trees." (Pariat, 335) Evelyn's search made her travel to colonial India and thereafter to Cherrapunjee. This journey exhibits myriad questions about the colonial treatment of indigenous knowledge, the forests, map-making, religion, agriculture, and the language in the particular area. When she enquires about the "Nonglaid" to Kong Bathsheba she was replied that "they are the ones who walk ...nomads". Evelyn scrutinized the word 'nomads' through her colonial lens and limited understanding of nomadic culture and asked Bathsheba whether the nomads possessed no home, to which Bathsheba replied:

I do not understand you people and why you always define things through lack. These are people with no alphabet. This is a place with no books. This is a place with no paintings. These are the people without Christ. These are people with no home. (330)

Reeju Ray questioned these half-baked theories propounded in Hooker's *Himalayan Journal* (1854) which stated the indigenous people as "savage" and "half-civilized" and that they have erroneous "knowledge of objects of natural history and a uniform nomenclature for them" (Hooker, 450). This statement of Hooker about indigenous Khasi people says Reeju Ray in her book *Placing the Frontier in British North East India* (2023) has "legitimized his representations, inferences, and conclusions." Even though it was Hooker's reliance on local knowledge to ultimately "build, develop, and legitimize all forms of colonial knowledge that were crucial for the empire." Hooker was awed by the brilliant picaresque formations done by the inosculation of the roots of fig trees which bridge the streams by forming natural grafts into what we call the living bridges. Evelyn finds in Hooker's journal that it was made for the Nonglaid to carry the Diengiei wherever they sought a safe abode for it. The tribes of trees are "brought under the purview of science, in the same way, the tribes of people living in these hills were brought under the influence of civilization." Yet his findings were incomplete because not all tribes welcomed outsider influence into their land. "This was not only an indication that his scientific inquiries were limited to the areas considered safe in the Khasi hills and the frontier in general." Hooker heavily depended on the local chief's assistance to formulate his journey inward thus making his journal incomplete. (114-116) Evelyn is

spellbound to witness these airborne bridges during her wanderings with her local guide Bah Khrawbor. When replied that it takes at least fifteen years to complete one bridge, she is:

Moved to silence, struck by how many decades it takes to create this, how much foresight is required, and patience. She sits on a boulder, away from the others, feeling that this place, with its deep pools and waterfalls, its glinting sunlight and butterflies, is where magic could happen. (Pariat, 358)

Hooker further presented a racialized scientific classification by stating that the Khasi people “are of the Indo-Chinese race” juxtaposing this with personality types “helpful, frank, unpleasant, intractable, and so on.” Even Hooker’s discovery of the differently shaped monoliths that spread across Khasi and Jaintia hills were “divorced from their relevant context and described only in relation to Stonehenge in Britain.” These discoveries “confirmed the universality of primitive societies and their crucial link in the civilizational chain.” The colonial spatialization of tribal spaces resulted in the imposition of temporal backwardness on those areas. The process of framing the discourse of people to be “primitive” and “backward” converted them “from being subject-agents of different histories to being objects of a totalizing representational knowledge.” (Ray, 119-121)

Evelyn accompanied by Mr. and Mrs. Wheeler travels to Cherrapunjee which was under British control. Mr. Wheeler informs her about regular skirmishes in these areas and about agricultural practices. The tribals practice shifting cultivation, very destructive from a colonial point of view because this form of agricultural practice required a process of slashing and burning the forest and the Britishers were trying to protect the forest by creating reserved areas. Madhav Gadgil and Ramachandra Guha in the book *This Fissured Land* (1992) said that shifting (jhum) agriculture was “life-encompassing”. Jhum has an overwhelming importance in structuring social life and it manifested itself “in the myths and legends constructed around it in tribal cosmology.” No doubt that the colonial administration disfavoured it because for them it is an “unremunerative form of agriculture in comparison with plough cultivation.” One reason for this animosity is “timber operations competed with jhum for territorial control of the forest. Shifting agriculture has regenerative quality because the cultivated land was “left fallow for an extended period, allowing the vegetation and soil to recoup and recover lost nutrients” and the cultivators moved to a new land to practice the same process again. (132-133) Evelyn’s conversation with Mr. Wheeler erupted into a squabble at the dinner table when she asked:

The sacred groves have been standing for hundreds of years without our intervention. Is it necessary to do this? Why must we take their forests and turn them into reserves? (Pariat, 353)

To which she is replied by Mr. Wheeler thus:

Yes, they have, but we find there is no strategy on their part to make any money from them. It's a waste. Added to that is the threat from unmonitored shifting cultivation. We are here to ensure a balance between conservancy, which is a priority for us, and sustainable profit. We are here to help. One day, when the empire is gone – and it will go, if you ask me - we will leave this model behind for them to follow. (Pariat, 354)

The Charter Act of 1813 allowed the missionaries to enter India and The English Education Act of 1835 expanded English education in the North Eastern Hills of India, both were “a milestone in the movement towards liberal, utilitarian reform in the colony.” Indigenous knowledge that exists there doesn't require a written language; its multifarious quality makes it one of the most unique systems of communication. Each clan spoke a different language and “standardization” of it was one of the key factors that brought the missionaries there. “Linguistic standardization was aided by a growing print and publishing industry in the second half of the nineteenth century.” (Ray, 136-137) When Evelyn asks a boy about his inclination toward a newer form of education, he replies:

Christianity had come to them now, and they could finally make progress. His people were in the light. (Pariat, 343)

Evelyn's maid Deng a Khasi girl finally helps her with her search for the Diengiei. She reveals that she is the daughter of a Nonglaid woman but as fate unfolds her mother is caught by the missionaries and was put in an orphanage. As per the Nonglaid rule, she was not taken back, yet Deng could communicate with her nomadic cousins. They have a unique form of communication. 'Kyrwoh', a pre-colonial form of writing is woven in a particular way to denote a particular message. To Evelyn, this was like some Celtic band but this type of messaging technique was used in this land since kings. Now only the Nonglaid knows it. Deng's words “Not everything that can be read is written on paper, memsahib” (Pariat, 361) make her understand that Khasi was not the only language used for communication. Writing was an important tool that administered the notion of “rhetoric of fixity”, for colonial domination. “Agreements with colonial authorities assumed fixity and unalterability” thereby

promoting new geography through special forms of writing, “such as surveying and mapping” every “demarcated territory and zones of control.” (Ray, 142) For Ajay Skaria, writing served not only as a tool but also as an ideological means to prioritize written communication in the administration and juridical proceedings. Skaria in his essay *Writing, Orality and Power in the Dangs, Western India, 1800s to 1920s* (1996) defines “rhetoric of fixity” as:

The notion that meanings once inscribed in writing were more stable and less arbitrary than those embodied in oral traditions or pre-colonial forms of writing. From this perspective, the inscription of colonial laws substituted a regular and ordered world for a personal tyrannical, and arbitrary one. This understanding extended to the necessary fictions surrounding the contract or the written word. (37)

This preference for writing over orality made huge gaps in understanding indigenous knowledge systems in the coming generations. The wisdom that once existed in oral traditions is now lost or on the verge of loss. Writing requires the validity of accepted norms and knowledge and the presence of the English-speaking Khasi middle-class people among the interpretive community “demonstrates a crucial shift in the way that writing superseded orality as the valid, reliable, and dominant source of knowledge in the hills.” (Ray, 143) Among the woods, Evelyn hits this realization about isolation, “To isolate is to deaden”. Isolating only the Khasi as a mode of written language is like isolating science from “unfathomable interconnectedness.” (Pariat, 366) Similarly giving these nomadic tribes a fixed place to stay is to take away their very essence of life that is movement. The Nongġaid was given a village to settle down in after independence for which “there was resistance, they fought, they perished – and now they exist only in song.” (Pariat, 436) These remaining pockets of oral practices in the form of folklore continue to thrive in villages like Mawmalang even today “unfazed by surrounding that are inimical to it.” Its manifestation is felt everywhere in the sacred groves of the folktales, oral poetry sung in different occasions, archery, women potters of the villages, chants, ballads, and songs throughout the tribal population in Meghalaya. (Syiem 2016, 82-83)

Evelyn finally meets Phyrnai, and Īada, the two Nongġaid siblings, and resumes her search for the Diengiei the knowledge only the nomads possess. They journey to the depths of the forest where life is bursting with all its vitality. From them, she gets to know the importance of movement. Moving from one place to another in every season keeps them alive, “to still is to be without life.” (388) They point out that movement from one land to the other in shifting cultivation allows for the cultivated land to rest and the fire set for clearing the land also

promotes new growth. Their journey halts when the siblings point towards “a glorious orchid in pristine, immaculate white” (394) stating that it is the Diengiei that she is searching which is not. The nomads play a game with the foreigners who come looking for the Diengiei and every time they point toward some beautiful orchid calling it the archetypal plant, some want to possess it and a few who don’t will eventually be taken to the Diengiei after they accept the rule to stay the rest of their lives with the nomads. Their reply to Evelyn was:

It is no small thing. To hold knowledge is to hold responsibility, and to know truly is to know deeply, to give of yourself so that the knowing means something more than mere words. True knowing changes you; we believe you cannot go back to how you were in the world before. It has always been this way...” (402)

Evelyn’s story remains open-ended. Shai’s journey to Mawmalang, and Domiasiat villages at the “edge of Meghalaya” (33) to see her sick nanny Oiñ and find a cure for her disease furthers our notice of the interdependence of all living beings. Teasing this balance will lead to destruction. She came to know about the uranium mining done by the Union Corporation of India Limited (UCIL) and the hazards caused by it in those regions. The radioactive waste generated by these extractions is hard to contain, “it runs like water, sits like stone, and rises in the air as dust.” (Pariat, 62) Rob Nixon in his book *Slow Violence and the Environmentalism of the Poor* (2011) talks about the effects of these forms of “attritional catastrophes” that leads towards displacement, “temporal, geographical, rhetorical, and technological displacements that simplify violence and underestimate, in advance and in retrospect, the human and environmental costs” thus making the places irretrievable for those who once resided them. These places don’t usually get attention from the mainstream media. (7) Monetising the wealth of the land has brought untold tragedies in the form of the death of human and nonhuman populations:

We noticed our birds were dying. Our cows and dogs going mad, our bay trees wilting, our fishes floating. Then our people started bleeding. (Pariat, 62)

This form of slow violence will result in “cultural loss synonymous with a language loss that will continue to decimate the speaking numbers who are turning their backs upon their forest and rivers” and make these forest tribes dumb spectators in a frenzy to catch up with the rest of the world. (Syiem 2016, 83-84) But Kong Spelity, also a character in Pariat’s novel, stood resolute against this violence. For her freedom:

is a thing in her hands, as real as mud and root and stone. It is family, and mother, and parent. (Pariat, 456)

Since the 1980s, “Kong Spelity noticed the hazardous impact of uranium mining activity caused around her” resulting in the deterioration of her family’s health and the death of her cattle. The impact of uranium mining in Domiasiat at large affected the health of living and non-living simultaneously and by putting a stop to it by refusing the money offered by the UCIL, she has become “an icon of the people in the state of Meghalaya to fight against uranium mining” (Lyngkhoi 2021, 26-30) Shai, being a person from the city, uprooted from Shillong and shifted to Delhi at a very early age gained a new perspective of life in those few days she stayed in Mawmalang. She has seen in cities a hierarchical framework where the landowners commodify labour and exploitation of resources is prevalent at all times. It is hard for them to think of land “not merely as a factor of production but as imagination, an Eden to live in.” (Pariat, 458) Crutzen hopes in his essay *The Anthropocene* (2006), that this epoch:

will not only be characterized by continued human plundering of Earth’s resources and dumping of excessive amounts of waste products in the environment, but also by vastly improved technology and management, wise use of Earth’s resources, control of human and domestic animal population, and overall careful manipulation and restoration of the natural environment. (17)

Conclusion

Indigenous communities all over the world experienced significant impacts due to extensive environmental disruptions, leading to disruptions in their cultures as well. These detrimental shifts were based on fundamental contrasts in beliefs about the nature of human and animal existence within the world between European and Indian perspectives. (Nixon, 11) The environmental activists have initiated a critical rescue endeavour aimed at preserving this deteriorating ecosystem. Their efforts underscore the imperative to safeguard the flora and fauna from decay, as it stands as our sole pathway to ensuring the survival of the ecological balance in the years ahead. The Indigenous people showcase that the vital form of knowledge is that of protection, conservation, rejuvenation, and regeneration. Ever since the time of hunter-gatherers the indigenous Khasis “have maintained a symbiotic relationship with the natural environment” which determined their history and also in the present day lived cultures in some remote areas of Meghalaya. The forest has left “an indelible mark” evident still today in the Khasi people’s customs, culture, and legends. (Shangpliang, 68) *The Anthropocene*

epoch posits a notable conflict between humans and nature, yet *Everything the Light Touches* by Janice Pariat prompts readers to procure a biophilic understanding of the environment where every species has a right to live on this planet thereby ensuring its sustainability. The destruction done in the colonial period can still be reclaimed in the postcolonial by the help of collective consciousness, species interconnectedness, and indigenous knowledge systems.

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